

Effectiveness of English Language Teaching Evaluation: Teachers' and Students' Perspectives at Undergraduate Level in Pakistan

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Abstract

This research study has been conducted to survey the English language teaching evaluation in universities/colleges in Pakistan with the aim to provide suggestions to teachers, curriculum developers and educational authorities for improving the English language teaching methods and techniques currently in use. Suggestions of English teachers of universities/colleges at undergraduate level are the main concern of the study on the other hand equal importance is given to the learning attitudes and opinions of the students. A descriptive investigation methodology, consisting of questionnaire, is utilized to evaluate and analyze the English teaching effectiveness. Both teachers and students consider evaluation of teaching effectiveness very important for the English language programs at the universities/colleges level. Among the other significant findings students are more concerned about how much they learn English in the class and they are less concerned about the grades they achieve in English language courses. The findings of this research study and suggestions of teachers and students for the English language teaching improvement can help teachers to modify their English language teaching methods, help students to adjust their learning attitudes and to stimulate curriculum development authorities to schematize English language teaching material and methods to facilitate teaching goals.

Keywords: language, students, teaching effectiveness

1. Introduction

In the recent years the English has become the language of science and technology and it is the common concern of the national education policies to teach English as second language (Seçer S. Y. E. & Erisen Y. 2020; Sifakis N. C, 2019). English language is said to be “world language” because in many countries of the world it is used as the official language and it is taught compulsorily in education system (Wallraf, 2000; Crystal, 2003). Beyond any doubt, together with networking, globalization, internet and integration English language has secured its position as a lingua franca of our time (Mauranen, 2009).

The aim of this study is to explore the college/university teachers' and students' perspectives on the effectiveness of English language teaching and to provide suggestions to curriculum designers for improving and upgrading the English language teaching methods currently in use. On the one hand, the suggestions of college/university English language teachers are the main concern and on the contrary students' learning attitudes and opinions is given equal attention including the interaction between the teachers and students.

Language learning activity includes the active learning of students. To understand the effectiveness of English language teaching one need to evaluate the language teaching activity. Evaluation includes a number of evaluative judgments like research and analysis. Teaching evaluation mainly consists on teacher's instruction and the contents covered in the course. The evaluation of teacher's teaching provides basis for students' guidance and remedial teaching methodology. According to Kibler (1979) the process of teaching has four sections, teaching goals, evaluation before learning, teaching activity and evaluation after teaching process.

In second language learning, students' feedback is not given much weightage and the teaching methods do not directly address their language learning needs and requirements. Every learner comes in the language class with some specific aims and objectives in mind. If the teachers consider the needs of the students and give weightage to their feedback can be helpful for students and the result of the language teaching and learning process would be much better. By considering the students perceptions the course designers will include the contents that will accelerate the language learning process.

The present study is significant for the English language learners at college/university level in Pakistani context. It helps the students to evaluate the effectiveness of English language teaching and learning. Students might be able to navigate their language learning potential along with the provided language teaching methods. The study also helps the teachers to improve their teaching methods and resources. The findings of the study might be helpful for the course designers to reconsider the language teaching contents in the courses that will help learners to learn language effectively. The study will also help to create mass awareness about the role of English learning methodologies and English language teaching.

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1.1. Research Questions

- How college/university teachers and students perceive the basic idea of English language teaching evaluation?
- How the results of English language teaching evaluation are implemented in college/university?

2. Literature Review

Teachers play an important role in the success of students' language learning abilities. Only those teachers attain success that possesses a sound knowledge of language and warmth in imparting their knowledge. Teachers' professional development programs play an important role in ensuring teachers' teaching competencies, attitudes and in-depth content knowledge (Zhiyong, Muthukrishnan & Sidhu, 2020). Teachers should pay their full attention to teaching process by utilizing the best practices to achieve the teaching goals. In the recent years the term evaluation is widely used in academia. According to Popham (1978) in Chinese history the activities of evaluation have long been existed. The modern types of evaluations have their basis in the United States. In 1892 Rice started a formal educational evaluation by starting public schools evaluation formally (Anderson, et al., 1975, pp. 141-142). Chiu (1970) stated that evaluation has been promoted by Thorndike in 1920's. And further it is formalized by Tyler and others in 1930's.

Different researchers and educationists have given different definitions and interpretations of the term evaluation. Following are the some interpretations of the term evaluation given by different scholars.

Stufflebeam (1971) defines evaluation as "a process in which useful data are recorded and collected, and provided for policy judgment and selection" (p. 58).

Tenbrink (1974) regards evaluation as "a process in which information is gathered and utilized to make judgment and provided to enact policy" (p. 8).

Tyler (1969) views evaluation "a process in which behavioral or work performance is compared with the specifically listed goals" (p. 62)

According to Patton, (2008) "evaluation is methodologically eclectic, pluralistic, and mixed" (p. 11).

Rossi, Lipsey, & Freeman (2004) define "evaluation is the use of social research methods to systematically investigate the effectiveness of social intervention programs"(p. 28).

Donaldson & Christie (2006) state that "evaluation generates information for decision making" (p. 250). According to Donaldson & Christie evaluation ask basic bottom-line questions like, For whom evaluation work better? What are the conditions in which it works? How do we make it better? Program evaluators provide answers to these defensible questions.

According to Russ-Eft & Preskill (2009) evaluation pose critical questions to seek the answers regarding how well a program, system, product, process, or organization is working (p. 6).

According to Li, Tsung-ming (1980) evaluation is "using all feasible evaluating skill to evaluate all of the effects expected by education" (p. 1983). He deems evaluation a series of processes in which objective scientific methods and subjective value judgment are utilized to conduct a reasonable review on educational contents and measures so as to know their advantages and disadvantages, to provide improvement strategies and to carry out the educational goals" (p. 108).

According to Scriven (2013) primary purpose of evaluation is to make decisions and its main purpose is to determine the worth or merit. (Hopson, & Caruthers, 2011); Russ-Eft & Preskill, 2009; Chen, 2015; Patton, 2008; Donaldson & Christie, 2006; Patton et al., 2014)

A synthesis of all the definitions given above considers evaluation as a scientific and systematic process of collecting data, and a judgment and utilization of data. Evaluation, viewed as a whole requires a number of processes that uses systematic methods to collect, review and measure data on the basis of reasonable standards to provide a reference for decision making.

Effectiveness of teaching and learning process cannot be analyzed effectively without evaluation. Teaching methods can be improved with proper evaluation methods. Since many opinions exist regarding evaluation of teaching in schools, colleges and universities, it is necessary to review the related literature of the field and establish the bases for this study. According to Huagn (1989) a teacher should have find understandings about the evaluation:

1. Evaluation is not used to compare the students' learning results with other students. If it is used for the comparison then it will cause the students an object of blame and accusation.
2. Evaluation should not used for the classification or grading of students rather it should be used to identify the opportunities for the improvement of teaching and learning.
3. Methods and tools of evaluation should be appropriate so it should not divert the learning process.
4. Evaluation is not a limited type of examinations rather it include methods such as practical work, written tests, oral tests and observations so that cognition skills can be include.
5. Evaluation tools should include the important content at each level of learners' behavior.

According to Li (1980) the aforementioned understandings for evaluation should be based on related research, and these basic teaching evaluation principals can be classified into six categories (p. 11-17).

Evaluation is a comprehensive term that goes ahead of simply measurement and numerical value. Evaluation includes both tangible and intangible value judgment to the numerical value. Due to its broader scope evaluation serves many functions. Hopkins (1989) suggests following five important functions of evaluation.

1. Evaluation helps the learners to understand their learning progress that enhance their learning abilities.
2. Evaluation provides insights about the learner's learning difficulties and help the teachers to formulate remedial teaching.
3. Evaluation helps teachers to understand students' learning achievements and their level of efforts.
4. Evaluation help teachers to analyze their teaching methods and effective practice that provides the basis to improve the teaching methods and materials.
5. Evaluation provides the relevant data that can be used by institutes' administrators as a basis for teaching learning improvement.

3. Research Methodology

This study used sampling surveys to collect the needed data. The questionnaire is adapted from the dissertation submitted by Chia-Chun Tung (1996) to the Florida International University, Miami Florida in the partial satisfaction of the requirements of the degree of doctor of Education. The sampling technique which was used in this study is three-stage cluster sampling (Scheaffer, et al., 1990). A three-stage cluster sample is obtained by three steps. The first step is to select a random sample of clusters (primary sampling units, psu), the second step is to select a random sample of elements (secondary sampling units, ssu) from each sampled cluster, and the third step is to select a random sample of elements (third sampling units, tsu) from each sampled secondary sampling units. Finally, combined these subsamples obtained from the third step to equal a three stage cluster sample. This sampling technique is largely used when the population size becomes large and such procedures, simple random sampling.

Stratified random sampling and systematic sampling, lead to several difficulties: One is the difficulty of preparing a frame. The second is the high cost of surveying scattered sampling units. And a third is the difficulty of administering a sampling plan where the sampling units are widely scattered. Based on the above reasons, this study chose three-stage cluster sampling to collect the needed data. Using this sampling technique, a list of all colleges/universities (which are offering MA or BS English programs) in Punjab was obtained and a simple random sample of colleges/universities were selected from all those colleges/universities, then a list of the classes in the colleges/universities that were selected in first stage provided the source of selection of a simple random sample of classes from each sampled colleges/universities, and third, a list of the teachers/students in the classes that were selected in the second stage provided the source of selection of a simple random sample of teachers and students respectively from each sampled classes

The population of this study included 50 public and private colleges/universities. The colleges/universities surveyed include fourteen colleges/universities. The subjects surveyed include 70 English teachers and 700 students of the fourteen colleges/universities. A sample is a collection of elements drawn from a population. Data are obtained from the elements of the sample and used in describing the population.

Table-1

	Universities/Colleges	Teachers	Students
1	COMSATS University Islamabad, Vehari Campus	5	50
2	National University of Modern Language (NUML), Islamabad, Multan Campus	5	50
3	Government Post Graduate College GPGC Burewala	5	50
4	University of Education, Lahore, Okara Campus	5	50
5	Ghazi University - Dera Ghazi Khan	5	50
6	Islamia University, Bahawalpur	5	50
7	University of Gujrat, Lahore Campus	5	50
8	Govt. College of Science, Multan	5	50
9	Government College University (GCU), Faisalabad	5	50
10	Emerson University Multan	5	50
11	University of Punjab, Lahore	5	50
12	Government Post Graduate College GPGC Vehari	5	50
13	University of Education, Lahore, DG Khan Campus	5	50
14	Institute of Southern Punjab, Multan	5	50

This research used Kibler's General Model of Instruction (GMI) to evaluate the English teaching of colleges/universities in Punjab, Pakistan. The GMI divides teaching process into four parts: teaching goals, pre-learning evaluation, teaching activities, and teaching evaluation. Following the GMI and using the collected basic data from the teachers and students formed this research structure.

According to the nature of the research questions the following statistical methods were used to confirm with the research purposes.

1. Relative frequency distribution was used to obtain the general views of the colleges/universities students and English teaching teachers on evaluation and its importance.
2. Comparative Studies: The general purpose of using comparative studies is to make comparisons of two populations of interest.
3. Chi-square Test: This method was used for goodness of fit tests and independence test
4. Correlation Analysis: The coefficient of correlation is a descriptive measure of the degree of linear relationship between X and Y.
5. Multivariate Analysis of Variance: This method was used to consider the statistical analysis of two groups of subjects on several dependent variables simultaneously.

4. Analysis

4.1. Analysis of Personal Information

The valid questionnaires obtained by this survey include 70 teachers and 700 students. Following is the analysis of the personal information obtained by the teachers and students.

Among the 70 teachers surveyed the 33 teachers are male and 37 are female. Four teachers graduated (14 years of education), 40 teachers were with master's degree (16 years of education), 9 teachers were holding masters of philosophy degree (18 years of education) and 17 teachers were holding PhD degree. 52 teachers specialized in English linguistics, 12 teachers majored in English literature, and 6 teachers specialized in English language and literature.

Among the 700 students surveyed 293 students are male and 407 are female. Almost 90% of the students surveyed are between 20 to 25 years old.

4.2. General Ideas of English Teaching Evaluation

This section describes the perception of teachers and students on the general ideas of English language teaching evaluation. It includes the importance of evaluation of learning achievement in English courses, level of need to evaluate speaking, listening, writing and reading skills, the current conducting situation of listening, speaking, reading and writing. Teachers' and students' suggestions to increase or reduce the evaluation of speaking, listening, writing reading and skills.

4.2.1. Teachers' and students' viewpoints on the "general ideas of English teaching evaluation"

Regarding the evaluation of students' learning achievement in English courses 91.4% teachers regarded it as important 2.9% responded as neutral and 5.7% regarded it unimportant. On the other hand 92.7% students regarded it very important to evaluate their learning achievement and 4.9% students responded as neutral and 2.5% students regarded an unimportant. Generally speaking the teachers and students responses are quite consistent regarding the importance of students' evaluation of learning achievement in English courses. Both teachers and students regarded the evaluation of achievement in English courses as highly important.

Figure 1: Importance of Evaluation

Figure 2 and 3 shows the level of need to evaluate Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing skills. Both teachers and students have given the greater weightage to speaking skill as compared with the other skills, 100 % teachers and 94.5 students regarded it very necessary. Teachers and students have given the importance to the listening skills at second place, 100% teachers and 94.5% students deemed listening skill necessary. Writing skill is rated at number three as 100% teachers and 92.7% students regarded writing skill necessary. Both teachers and students considered less important as compared to the other skills, 98.6% teachers and 88.7% students considered the reading skill necessary.

Figure 2: View of Teachers' on the Level of Need for Evaluate Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing

Figure 3: View of Students' on the Level of Need of Evaluate Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing

4.2.2. The Evaluation of Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing

Figure 4: Views of Teacher on Evaluation Frequency of Language Skill

Figure 5: Views of Students on Evaluation Frequency of Language Skills

Figure 4 shows the teachers’ responses for conducting the evaluation of writing skill is 97.1% that they conduct evaluation of writing more frequently. Evaluation of speaking skill is also regarded as frequently evaluated skill by the 90% of the teachers while 87.2% teachers regarded reading skill as frequently evaluated skill. Listening skill the seldom evaluated skill as 20% teachers responded that they seldom evaluate listening skill. On the other hand figure 5 shoes that according to the 80% students, teachers evaluate listening, speaking and writing skill more frequently and 25% students regarded reading skill as seldom evaluated skill.

4.2.3. Suggestions for the Evaluation of Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing

Figure 6: Teachers' Suggestions to Evaluate Language Skills

Figure 7: Students' Suggestions to Evaluate Language Skills

Figure 6 and 7 shows that both 95.7% teachers and 74.1% students suggested that evaluation for the speaking skill should be much increased and 100% teachers suggested that listening skill should be much increased. Student's responses are consistent regarding the increase of evaluation of listening, reading and writing, however both teachers 9% and students 20% suggested that writing skill should be maintained on the present conduction level.

4.2.4. Importance of the purpose of evaluating students' learning achievement

Figure 8: Teachers' Views on the Importance of the purpose of evaluating students' learning achievement

4.3. Variables

- A: Understanding learning effects
- B: Diagnosing learning difficulty
- C: Understanding reaching the level of teaching goal
- D: Understanding students' positions in social groups
- E: Understanding the situation of the learning process
- F: Improving teaching

Figure 9: Students' Views on the Importance of the purpose of evaluating students' learning achievement

4.4. Variables

- A: Understanding learning effects
- B: Diagnosing learning difficulty
- C: Understanding reaching the level of teaching goal
- D: Understanding students' positions in social groups
- E: Understanding the situation of the learning process
- F: Improving teaching

Figure 8 shows that 54.3% teachers have given the highest priority to the “diagnosing learning difficulty” of the students and they have given the second priority to “understanding the situation of the learning process” and “understanding reaching the level of teaching goal”. While figure 9 shows that 40.9% students have given the highest priority to “understanding learning effects” and they have given almost equal weightage to the “diagnosing learning difficulty”, “understanding reaching the level of teaching goal”, “understanding students' positions in social groups”, “understanding the situation of the learning process and improving teaching.

The analysis of the variance of teacher’s and students’ viewpoints on "the general ideas of the English teaching evaluation” vs. their individual backgrounds

The individual background of the teachers includes age, sex, years of teaching and educational levels. The Students’ background data consist of gender and major fields. To explore the difference of each variable in evaluation generalizations one-way analysis of variance is used and the Scheff Method of Multiple Comparison is used to test the results obtained.

1. Regardless of the gender of the teachers and students, there is no difference in the viewpoint of “the importance of English teaching evaluation”. All the teachers and students have given equal importance to evaluate English teaching.
2. Regardless of the different fields of the students there is no difference in the students’ major fields and their viewpoints of the importance of English teaching evaluation.
3. Regardless of the gender of the teachers there is no difference in the necessity of listening, speaking, reading and writing skills.
4. Regardless of the gender of the students there is no difference in the necessity of listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. All the students regarded
5. There is a significant difference on the current conducting situation of listening, speaking, reading and writing skills in each university. Further Scheffe method of multiple comparison of means is used to discover the difference level, but in the detailed comparison there is not found any significant difference in any university regarding the conducting situation of listening, speaking, reading and writing skills.
6. There is a significant difference in the level of need of four language skills listening, speaking, reading and writing. Further Scheffe method of multiple comparison of means is used to discover the difference level, in the detailed comparison there is a significant difference found regarding the level of need of listening skill between COMSATS University Islamabad and other universities, the mean difference of COMSATS University is greater than the other universities that ranges from 0.62 to 0.88. There is not found any significant difference regarding the level of need for listening skill between COMSATS and NUMUL University. After conducting the detailed comparison regarding the level of need for speaking skill it is found that although universities are different but there is no significant difference found. Regarding the level of need for reading skill it is found that there no significant difference between COMSATS University and NUMUL University but there is a significant difference found between COMSATS and all other universities as students of COMSATS University has given more importance to the reading skill as compared to other universities. The mean difference of COMSATS University is greater than the other universities that ranges from 0.56 to 0.1. Further the detailed mean comparison of Scheffe method surfaced that besides COMSATS University there is a significant difference regarding the level of need for the reading skill between NUMUL University and all the other universities. The mean difference of NUMUL University is greater than the other universities that ranges from 1 to 1.44. There is a significant difference regarding the writing skill between COMSATS University and all the other universities as the mean difference of COMSATS University is greater than the other universities that ranges from 0.58 to 1.6.

4.5. Problems related to English Teaching Evaluation Research

This section covers the analysis of the items related to examination tests, level of difficulty of examination questions, examination content, the difficulty level of examination questions, the reflection of students’ ability by their examination grades, importance of teaching goals, teaching content and students’ ability in designing the examination questions.

4.6. The General View of Teachers and Students on the Problems Related to English Teaching Evaluation

Figure 10 shows that over 97% of the teachers are of the view that examination tests given to class meet the teaching goals, only 3% of the teachers considered the examination tests as not capable of meeting the teaching goals. Further figure 11 indicates that 49% of the teachers regard the examination questions given to the classes are moderate, not too difficult not too easy, 35% of the teachers considered the exam questions as difficult and only 17% of the teachers regarded the exam questions as easy. On the other hand 41% students considered the exam question as moderate, 45% students considered exam questions as difficult and only 14% students regarded exam questions as easy. Although the responses of teachers and students are uniform but the percentage of students is higher who responded as “too difficult” as compared with the teachers.

Figure 10: Teachers' Views on the Students' Grades Representation

Figure 11: Teachers' and Students' Views on Difficulty level of Exam Questions

4.7. The Items which should be considered in designing examination questions (Teaching Goals, Teaching Contents, Students' Ability)

Figure 12: Teachers' Preferences While Designing Exam Questions

Figure 13: Students' Preferences While Designing Exam Questions

Figure 12 indicates that 75% of the teachers first consider “teaching contents” and “students’ ability” while designing the examination questions and they have given less importance to “teaching goals” in designing examination questions. On the contrary figure 13 shows that 60% of the students are of the view that teachers should consider “students’ ability” first when they design examination questions, and “teaching contents” at second place and “teaching goals” at third place. That’s why there is a significant difference in the optional items responses by Chi-squares test. Such responses may serve as guide to for the teachers in designing examination questions.

An analysis of the difference among university/college teachers’ and students’ personal backgrounds versus “the items related to English teaching evaluation”

1. There is no significant difference in the views of students on “the level of difficulty of examination questions” based on sex.
2. There is a significant difference in the “level of difficulty of examination questions based on students’ major fields. Further Scheffe method of multiple comparison of means is used to discover the difference level, in the detailed comparison there is not found any significant difference in the “level of difficulty of examination questions based on students’ major fields.

5. Findings

The aim of this research study was to explore the effectiveness of English teaching evaluation within Pakistani universities/colleges. Both the teachers and the students have given equal importance to the English language learning evaluation and English learning attitudes. Teachers’ and students’ viewpoints are different regarding the purpose of evaluating students’ learning achievements as teachers considered “diagnosing learning difficulty” as the main purpose of evaluating students’ learning achievements and they have given the least importance to “improving teaching” and “understanding students’ positions in social groups”. While according to the students the purpose of evaluation of students’ learning achievement is “understanding learning effects” and they have given almost equal importance to “diagnosing learning difficulty”, “understanding reaching the level of teaching goal”, “understanding students’ positions in social groups”, “understanding the situation of the learning process” and “improving teaching” as the purpose of evaluating students’ learning achievements.

There is no difference of views of teachers and students on the bases of their gender as all the male teachers/students and female teachers/students have given importance to the evaluation of English language abilities.

As for as the difference between the students’ major fields and their viewpoints on the importance of English teaching evaluation is concerned the students from all the fields regarded the language teaching evaluations as extremely important.

As for as the difference between gender, of the teachers and students, and the necessity of listening, speaking, reading and writing is concerned there is no significant difference. All the male and female teachers and students regarded English language evaluation very necessary. Further according to the students there is no significant difference on the current conducting situation of listening, speaking, reading and writing in each university, as teachers evaluate all the skills uniformly.

There is a significant difference in the level of need of four language skills. The students of COMSATS University Islamabad, Vehari campus and NUMUL University, Multan campus have given more importance to the necessity of

evaluation of listening and reading skills as compared with the other university students. There is no difference regarding the significance of evaluation of speaking and writing skills as students from all the universities considered it very necessary to evaluate speaking and writing skills.

5.1. Items related to English teaching evaluation

- Most of the surveyed teachers believe that English evaluation contents given to the students they teach match the English teaching goals.
- All the teachers and students believe that the examination questions given to the students to evaluate English abilities are neither too difficult nor too easy.
- Teachers give the first priority to the “teaching contents” while designing the examination questions and they give second importance to students’ ability and the third place to the “teaching goals”. On the other hand students are of the view that teachers should consider “students’ abilities” while designing examination questions. Both teachers and students have given the least importance to the “teaching goals” while designing examination questions.
- As for as the view points of the students are concerned regarding the difference between their “gender” and the “level of difficulty” of examination questions there is no difference as male and female both regard examination questions moderate not too difficult nor too easy. Further there is no difference of student’s views on the base of their “major fields” and the “level of difficulty” of examination questions.

6. Discussion

This study provides the general views of teachers and students on the English teaching evaluation and compares the difference of their views on evaluation based on gender, age, serving institute/learning institute, years of teaching/learning and major fields in order to provide reference to teachers, students and university/college administration. Evaluation of students’ learning achievement and attitudes help the teachers to understand their learning interests and abilities. Understanding students’ learning interests and abilities serve as reference for the teachers in selecting teaching materials, teaching methods and setting teaching goals. It also help the teachers to understand the students’ progressive learning situation as well as to diagnose their learning difficulty. On the contrary such evaluations provide the teachers a chance to understand their teaching shortcomings and strengths to improve their teaching instructions. For the students, learning evaluation triggers their learning motivation, as good learning results further motivate students to learn.

Teachers are of the view that the purpose of evaluation is to diagnose the learning difficulties of the students while students are of the view that the main purpose of the evaluation is to understand the learning effects. Students have a broader view regarding the purpose of evaluation although they have given more weightage to learning effects as the purpose of learning achievements however they think that evaluation provides a chance to understand students’ learning difficulty, teaching goals, students’ position in class and improving teaching methods.

Teachers and students views are not consistent regarding the need for evaluating students’ English abilities. Students have given almost equal importance to the level of need for the evaluation of listening, speaking, reading and writing skills and they are of the view that these skills are evaluated with the same frequency. As for as teachers are of the view that evaluation of speaking skill is very necessary to evaluate as compared with the other skills and it is less often evaluated than writing skill. They have given second place to listening and third place to writing. Teachers considered reading as more often evaluated language skill and they deemed it the least important language skill to be evaluated. Students suggested that to add more time to evaluate all the four language skills but the teachers suggested to add more time to evaluate speaking and listening skills.

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